

ISic0760

I.Sicily inscription 0760

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Piazza Armerina

Place of origin (modern)

Piazza Armerina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Piazza Armerina, private collection

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175796

EDCS 6100289

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1989.0344c

Manganaro, G. 1993. Greco nei pagi e latino nelle città della Sicilia romana tra I e VI sec. d.C.. In Calbi, A., Donati, A., Poma, G.(eds.), *l'epigrafia del villaggio*.

Faenza. pp. 543-594. At 573

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 187 no.73 fig.78

Manganaro, G. 2005. Note storiche ed epigrafiche per la villa (praetorium) del Casale di Piazza Armerina. *Sicilia Antiqua*. 2: 173-191. At 188 fig.30-30bis

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